

Unveiling the Uncommon: Choroideremia in a Female Patient

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CLINICAL IMAGE

A 26-year-old Hispanic female was referred to our clinic due to peripheral retinal changes seen during a routine evaluation elsewhere and an initial diagnosis of Retinitis Pigmentosa (RP). The patient reported no visual complaints, and past medical and family history was unremarkable. On examination, the best corrected visual acuity was 20/25 and 20/20 on the right eye (OD) and left eye (OS), respectively. Slit-lamp biomicroscopy revealed a normal anterior segment examination in both eyes. Fundus examination of both eyes showed chorioretinal atrophy mid-peripherally and centrally, except for a portion of preserved tissue in the macula (Figure 1A-D). These findings directed us to perform a retinal inherited disorders panel of 330 genes using genomic DNA extracted from a blood sample using standard protocols. Genetic studies showed a heterozygous pathogenic (deletion in exons 1-2) mutation in the CHM gene, leading to Choroideremia (CHM) diagnosis.

Figure 1: Color fundus (**Figure 1A-B**) and Fundus autofluorescence (**Figure 1C-D**) imaging revealed localized asymmetrical areas of chorioretinal atrophy between fellow eyes, with mottling of the retinal pigment epithelium in the periphery

Choroideremia, with an estimated incidence of 1 in 50,000, is an X-linked recessive disorder resulting from a mutation in the CHM gene located on chromosome Xq21^[1]. Choroideremia is linked to the gradual degeneration of the retinal pigment epithelium, choriocapillaris, and photoreceptors^[2]. Symptoms are mainly expressed in male patients and include progressive peripheral vision loss, night blindness, and later central vision loss, similar to other chorioretinal dystrophies; however, female carriers are primarily asymptomatic but can present with patchy chorioretinal atrophy^[2-3]. Inherited retinal diseases are considered a significant cause of sight loss in the working-age population, yet our patient experiences misdiagnosis, highlighting the challenge of low interest in genetic testing.

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